

Effect of *recA* inactivation on mutagenesis of *Escherichia coli* exposed to sublethal concentrations of antimicrobials

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Objectives: Low concentrations of some antibiotics have been reported to stimulate mutagenesis and recombination, which may facilitate bacterial adaptation to different types of stress, including antibiotic pressure. However, the mutagenic effect of most of the currently used antibiotics remains untested. Furthermore, it is known that in many bacteria, including *Escherichia coli*, stimulation of mutagenesis is mediated by the SOS response. Thus, blockage or attenuation of this response through the inhibition of RecA has been proposed as a possible therapeutic adjuvant in combined therapy to reduce the ability to generate antibiotic-resistant mutants. The aim of this work was to study the capacity of sublethal concentrations of antimicrobials of different families with different molecular targets to increase the mutant frequency of *E. coli*, and the effect that inactivation of *recA* would have on antibiotic-mediated mutagenesis.

Methods: We tested the mutagenicity of the following antimicrobials: ampicillin; ceftazidime; imipenem; fosfomicin; ciprofloxacin; trimethoprim; sulfamethoxazole; trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole; colistin; tetracycline; gentamicin; rifampicin; and chloramphenicol.

Results: Eight out of the 13 antimicrobials tested stimulate *E. coli* mutagenesis (slightly in most cases), with trimethoprim, alone or in combination with sulfamethoxazole, producing the highest effect. Inactivation of *recA* abolishes the mutagenic effect and also produces increased susceptibility to some of the tested antimicrobials.

Conclusions: The fact that inactivation of *recA* reduces mutagenicity and/or increases the activity of a large number of antimicrobials supports the hypothesis that RecA inhibition might have favourable effects on antibiotic therapy.

Keywords: mutations, antibiotic resistance, trimethoprim, sulfamethoxazole

Introduction

It has been demonstrated that some antimicrobials, such as fluoroquinolones and β -lactams, increase mutagenesis in bacteria via the induction of error-prone DNA polymerase expression.¹⁻³ Also, we have shown that the cephalosporin ceftazidime elicits adaptive responses, including increases in mutant frequency, in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.⁴ In addition, it is known that subinhibitory concentrations of the fluoroquinolone antibiotic ciprofloxacin promote genetic recombination in *Escherichia coli*.^{5,6} Very recently, Kohanski *et al.*³ have demonstrated that sublethal concentrations of some bactericidal antibiotics induce mutagenesis and that this induction correlates with an increase in reactive oxygen species (ROS), which in turn produces induction of the SOS response.⁷

Therefore, it is likely that some antibiotic treatments may influence the appearance of antibiotic-resistant bacteria through SOS mutagenesis⁸⁻¹⁰ or a combined effect of ROS and SOS mutagenesis.¹¹ Consequently, abolition or attenuation of the SOS response has been proposed as a possible therapeutic adjuvant in combined therapy to reduce the capacity to generate antibiotic-resistant mutants.^{8,12,13}

In many bacterial species, such as *E. coli*, DNA-damaging agents trigger the SOS response, which involves the induction of *recA* expression. Contact with single-stranded DNA (ssDNA) activates the coprotease activity of the RecA protein, which promotes self-cleavage of LexA, the SOS transcriptional repressor, and leads to increased transcription of the SOS response regulon.^{14,15} The autogenous control of *lexA* transcription

supports a cellular response that is exquisitely proportional to the DNA damage level and prevents false triggering of the SOS response.¹⁶ RecA has multiple functions that affect different cellular processes, such as the rescue of stalled replication forks,^{17,18} coprotease action involved in the self-cleavage of LexA and UmuD,¹⁹ promotion of homologous recombination,²⁰ control of swarming motility²¹ and the behaviour of bacteria in biofilms.²²

In this work we explored whether low concentrations of a representative group of antimicrobials of different classes may contribute to genetic variation by affecting mutagenesis in *E. coli* and, as a consequence, favour the emergence of antibiotic resistance by mutation. In addition, we studied whether inactivation of *recA* reduces or prevents this induced mutagenesis. The tested antimicrobials or combinations were ampicillin, ceftazidime, imipenem, fosfomicin, ciprofloxacin, trimethoprim, sulfamethoxazole, trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole, colistin, tetracycline, gentamicin, rifampicin and chloramphenicol.

Materials and methods

Bacterial strains, plasmids and medium

The *E. coli* K-12 strains used were MG1655, ME12 (MG1655 *lacZΔC-lacZΔN-yfp*) and an ME12 $\Delta recA::kan$ derivative.²³ The construction of ME12 strains has previously been described.^{6,23} The *recA* phenotype was verified by measuring UV sensitivity. The plasmid pSC101-*PrecA::GFP* harbours a green fluorescent protein (GFP) transcriptional fusion after the promoter of the *recA* gene.²⁴ Luria-Bertani medium (LB) was prepared according to Miller.²⁵ MICs of antibiotics for ME12 and ME12*recA* were determined according to CLSI recommendations,²⁶ except that the bacterial inocula were identical to those used in all subsequent mutagenesis experiments. Antibiotics tested for stimulation of mutation were used at different concentrations around their MICs.

Mutagenesis experiments

Mutant frequencies were studied as described.^{6,23} Briefly, for mutant frequency measurement, 2 mL aliquots of exponentially growing cells (10^8 cells/mL) were incubated with different concentrations of antibiotic for 4 h at 37°C with shaking (250 rpm). One mL of these cultures was centrifuged for 10 min at 6000 rpm in a minifuge. The pellet was resuspended in 2 mL of fresh LB medium and incubated overnight at 37°C with shaking. This step is necessary to resolve the filaments formed after treatment with some antibiotics, such as ciprofloxacin, ceftazidime, trimethoprim and trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole. Resolution of filaments was verified by direct observation of samples from the different cultures under the microscope. Only cultures with a proportion of filaments of <5% of total cells were plated. Viable cells were determined by plating appropriate dilutions onto LB agar plates. Mutant frequencies were calculated as the number of colonies growing on rifampicin (100 mg/L) or fosfomicin (10 mg/L) plates per viable colony. At least three independent experiments were performed for each antibiotic concentration, and three more, with five replicas each, for the most mutagenic concentrations observed. For the experiments with the *recA* mutant, five independent experiments were performed for each concentration.

Effect of antibiotics on *recA* expression

To qualitatively assess the antibiotic-mediated induction of transcription from the *recA* promoter the strain ME12 containing the pSC101-*PrecA::GFP* reporter plasmid was used. A 100 μ L aliquot of an overnight culture was inoculated into LB soft agar (0.7% agar) and

spread onto LB plates. Antibiotic-containing filter discs were deposited onto the agar and plates were visualized through a blue-light lamp after 24 h of incubation at 37°C. Discs with mitomycin-C (10 μ g), a known inducer of the SOS system, or without antibiotic were used as a positive or negative control, respectively.

Effect of antibiotics on cell morphology

The effect of low concentrations of antibiotics on cell morphology was studied by direct observation of the treated cultures under an Olympus BX61 microscope. Aliquots (2 mL) of exponentially growing ME12 cells ($\sim 10^8$ cells/mL) were incubated with different antibiotics for 4 h at 37°C with shaking (250 rpm). After 4 h of treatment, 2 μ L from each culture was used to prepare samples. These samples were scanned and photographed under the microscope with a UplanF1 100 \times NA 1.30 oil immersion objective.

Statistical analysis

Statistical evaluation was done by using the Mann-Whitney *U*-test when two groups were compared. Differences were considered significant when *P* values were ≤ 0.05 .

Results

Effect of different concentrations of antimicrobials on *E. coli* mutagenesis

In principle, mutagenic activity of antimicrobials is expected to occur within a window of concentrations very close to the MIC (peri-MIC), because higher concentrations will kill or stop the growth of most of the cells in the population and lower ones will not have a stimulatory effect.²⁷ In this work, we investigated the mutagenic effect of 13 antimicrobials at peri-MIC concentrations on the strain ME12, an MG1655 derivative, by evaluating the appearance of mutants resistant to rifampicin or fosfomicin. We used the strain ME12 for consistency, because it was used to study the effect of the same antibiotics on homologous recombination.^{5,6} This strain shows a spontaneous frequency of rifampicin-resistant mutants of 2×10^{-7} and of fosfomicin-resistant mutants of 1×10^{-6} (not shown). Table 1 shows the MIC of each antimicrobial under our experimental conditions for the strain ME12. The mutagenic effect was tested for five different concentrations, including two lower and two higher than the MIC and the MIC (i.e. 1/4 \times MIC, 1/2 \times MIC, MIC, 2 \times MIC and 4 \times MIC). The concentration of each antimicrobial producing the highest effect was re-tested using five independent replicates to confirm the results. Ten antimicrobials (ampicillin, ceftazidime, imipenem, fosfomicin, ciprofloxacin, trimethoprim, sulfamethoxazole, trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole, colistin and tetracycline) produced statistically significant increases ($P \leq 0.05$) in mutant frequency when it was calculated for rifampicin resistance, with maximal increases of 3.4-, 2.2-, 3.0-, 5.0-, 2.0-, 17.1, 6.3-, 8.7-, 3.0- and 2.1-fold, respectively (Figure 1a, black bars). The results from the other three drugs were not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). When the mutagenic effect was studied calculating the mutant frequency for fosfomicin resistance, eight antimicrobials (ampicillin, ceftazidime, imipenem, ciprofloxacin, trimethoprim, sulfamethoxazole, trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole and tetracycline) produced statistically significant increases ($P \leq 0.05$) in mutant frequency, with maximal

Table 1. MICs (mg/L) of the antimicrobials used in this study for the wild-type strain ME12 and its *recA* derivative

Antibiotic	ME12	ME12 Δ <i>recA</i>
Ampicillin	1	1
Ceftazidime	0.25	0.12
Imipenem	0.12	0.12
Fosfomycin	0.06	0.03
Ciprofloxacin	0.12	0.007
Trimethoprim	0.5	0.25
Sulfamethoxazole	256	256
Trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole ^a	0.5/9.5	0.25/4.75
Colistin	8	2
Tetracycline	0.5	0.5
Gentamicin	0.5	0.5
Rifampicin	2	2
Chloramphenicol	2	2

^aThe proportions of trimethoprim and sulfamethoxazole in trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole are 1:19, as indicated by EUCAST (http://eucast.www137.server1.mensemmedia.net/clinical_breakpoints).

increases of 3.6-, 2.0-, 2.2-, 2.2-, 7.7-, 4.9, 7.9- and 3.0-fold, respectively (Figure 1b, black bars). The results from the other five drugs were not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). Taken together, these results indicate that at least 8 out of 13 antimicrobials or combinations (those with positive results in both tests) produced increased mutagenesis levels at concentrations close to their MICs. Interestingly, while most antimicrobials produced mild increases in mutagenesis, trimethoprim, sulfamethoxazole and trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole produced the highest increases in mutant frequency in both tests (rifampicin and fosfomycin resistance). As stated in the Materials and methods section, the resolution of filaments was verified by direct observation of samples from the different cultures under the microscope before plating, and only cultures with a proportion of filaments of <5% of total cells were plated. Thus, increased mutant frequency is not attributable to the presence of filamented cells in the treated cultures. A description of the effect of antibiotic treatment on cell morphology can be found below.

As the number of viable bacteria in the inoculum (after antibiotic treatment) might affect the observed frequency of mutants, we performed experiments with different inoculum sizes of untreated ME12 cells, ranging from 10^7 to 10^9 cells. No differences were observed in mutant frequency between these cultures (not shown). Thus, the final number of viable cells after treatment with different drugs was not the cause of the observed antibiotic-mediated stimulation of mutagenesis.

Finally and remarkably, treatment with rifampicin or fosfomycin did not produce an increased number of rifampicin- or fosfomycin-resistant mutants, respectively, thus indicating that the concentrations of these antibiotics and/or the time of exposure used in our experiments were not able to select for rifampicin- or fosfomycin-resistant variants.

SOS induction by different antimicrobials

The induction of the SOS stress response by some antimicrobials has been previously described.^{1,2,7,28,29} To determine whether

the observed stimulation of mutagenesis could be linked to SOS induction, we studied the effect of these antimicrobials on the induction of *recA* transcription. We used the disc-plate assay described in the Materials and methods section. Figure 2 shows that ampicillin, ceftazidime, ciprofloxacin, trimethoprim, sulfamethoxazole and trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole induce transcription of the *recA*::GFP fusion, with the highest induction produced by ciprofloxacin, trimethoprim and trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole.

Effect of RecA on antibiotic-mediated stimulation of mutagenesis

It has been demonstrated that ciprofloxacin and ceftazidime stimulate mutagenesis in *E. coli* through the induction of mutagenic DNA polymerases of the SOS system.^{1,2} Consequently, we decided to study the effect of the different antimicrobials on mutant frequency in a *recA*-deficient background. As in the case of the wild-type strain, MICs of the different drugs were obtained for the *recA* strain (Table 1). As expected, a strong decrease in ciprofloxacin MIC was observed between the wild-type and its *recA*-deficient derivative. Also, small though consistent decreases were observed in the MICs of ceftazidime, fosfomycin, trimethoprim, trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole and colistin.

The effects of drugs on the mutant frequency of the *recA*-deficient derivative were studied with different peri-MIC concentrations, including the MIC itself. The mutagenesis stimulated by ampicillin, imipenem, ciprofloxacin, trimethoprim, trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole and tetracycline is abolished in the *recA* background (Figure 1a and b). Grey bars show the results with concentrations equivalent to the most mutagenic in the *recA*-proficient strain. None of the concentrations tested showed increased mutagenesis in the *recA*-deficient strain (except ceftazidime in the rifampicin-resistance test). Therefore, RecA is absolutely necessary for the stimulation of mutagenesis by the eight antimicrobials with positive results in both rifampicin- and fosfomycin-resistance tests.

Effect of mutagenesis-stimulating concentrations of antimicrobials on cell morphology

The effect of peri-MIC concentrations of antimicrobials on cell morphology (only the most stimulating concentrations are shown in Figure 3) were studied. Figure 3(a) shows that ampicillin, ciprofloxacin, trimethoprim, sulfamethoxazole and trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole, and the SOS inducer mitomycin-C (positive control) produced, as expected, a clear filamentation of ME12 cells after 4 h of treatment. A slight cell enlargement can be seen with tetracycline. In addition, imipenem produced classical ball-shaped cells. We also studied the effect of the corresponding antimicrobial concentrations (see above) on the *recA*-deficient strain. Figure 3(b) shows that, as predicted from its mechanism of action (inhibition of the septation process via protein PBP3), ceftazidime also produced filaments in the *recA* mutant. Amazingly, ciprofloxacin and trimethoprim (and sulfamethoxazole to a lesser extent) produced filaments in the *recA* derivative, although shorter than in the wild-type. This is an unexpected result as the production of filaments by these antibiotics was believed to be caused by induction of the SOS

Figure 1. Effect of sublethal concentrations of antimicrobials on mutant frequency. Fold changes in mutant frequency of the wild-type (wt) strain ME12 (black bars) and its *recA* mutant derivative (grey bars) for rifampicin resistance (RIF^R) (a) and fosfomycin resistance (FOS^R) (b), after treatment with antibiotics. Data are relative to untreated controls (no antibiotic). Only concentrations with the highest change in mutant frequency are represented. The number in parentheses below the antibiotic indicates the concentration relative to its MIC. Values are the means of five experiments \pm SD. Asterisks indicate that the fold increases relative to the untreated strain are statistically significant ($P \leq 0.05$, according to the Mann-Whitney *U*-test). AMP, ampicillin; CAZ, ceftazidime; IPM, imipenem; CIP, ciprofloxacin; TMP, trimethoprim; SUL, sulfamethoxazole; SXT, trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole; CST, colistin; TET, tetracycline; GEN, gentamicin; CHL, chloramphenicol.

system (see below). Thus, according to our results, a *recA*-independent mechanism of filamentation can be predicted.

Discussion

The extended use of antimicrobial drugs over the past six decades has had a major impact on human-associated bacteria (both commensals and pathogens), leading to the selection and spread of resistant variants. The exposure of bacteria to antibacterial agents results in the selection of pre-existing resistant variants that ultimately become fixed in the population.^{30–32} Antibiotic pressure may also select for bacteria with an increased mutation rate (hypermutators),³³ increasing the probability of bacteria becoming resistant.

Induction of the SOS response by antimicrobials such as fluoroquinolones, and increased mutagenesis as a consequence was described a long time ago (see Ysern *et al.*² and references therein). Because the SOS response is efficiently activated by DNA-damaging agents and this activation leads to the transcriptional induction of error-prone DNA polymerases, it is not surprising that clear evidence of antimicrobial-induced mutagenesis was first described with fluoroquinolones.^{2,34} However, induction of the SOS response, and its resultant increased mutagenesis, by β -lactams was described many years later.^{1,28}

A recent article has demonstrated that some antimicrobials, defined as bactericidal, such as ampicillin, norfloxacin and kanamycin, stimulate the production of highly deleterious ROS radicals in Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria, which

Figure 2. Effect of antibiotics on the transcription of the *recA::GFP* fusion on a solid surface. An aliquot of 100 μ L of an overnight culture was inoculated into LB soft agar (0.7% agar) and spread onto LB plates. Antibiotic-containing filter discs were deposited onto the gelified agar, and plates were visualized under a blue-light lamp after 16 h of incubation at 37°C. Induction is observed as a fluorescent band around the inhibition halo produced by ampicillin, ceftazidime, ciprofloxacin, trimethoprim, sulfamethoxazole and trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole. This assay permits the exploration of the full range of antibiotic concentrations for SOS induction without knowing the most effective one. The discs contain different amounts of antibiotic: ampicillin (AMP; 500 μ g); ceftazidime (CAZ; 10 μ g); imipenem (IPM; 40 μ g); fosfomycin (FOS; 100 μ g); ciprofloxacin (CIP; 10 μ g); trimethoprim (TMP; 300 μ g); sulfamethoxazole (SUL; 3200 μ g); trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole (SXT; 13.5/256 μ g); colistin (CST; 200 μ g); tetracycline (TET; 100 μ g); gentamicin (GEN; 200 μ g); rifampicin (RIF; 200 μ g); and chloramphenicol (CHL; 300 μ g). Discs containing no antibiotic (No Ab) or 10 μ g of mitomycin-C (Mito), a known inducer of the SOS system, were used as negative and positive controls, respectively.

ultimately can contribute to cell death.⁷ In contrast, bacteriostatic drugs do not produce such an effect. Interestingly, the cited article also shows that the same bactericidal drugs induce the SOS stress response and that inactivation of RecA, a co-regulator of the response, produces increased susceptibility to some of them, including norfloxacin, ampicillin and kanamycin.^{7,35} Our results show that mutagenesis is induced not only by bactericidal drugs but also by bacteriostatic ones, and that inactivation of RecA activity abolishes the induction of mutagenesis in all cases.

An interesting result from our investigation is that trimethoprim alone, but also in combination with sulfamethoxazole, promotes the highest increase in mutant frequency (Figure 1a and b). Trimethoprim prevents incorporation of thymine into bacterial DNA by inhibition of dihydrofolate reductase.³⁶ This provokes not only the induction of the SOS response,³⁷ but also a nucleotide pool imbalance that can affect replication fidelity.^{38,39} Therefore, both SOS response and nucleotide imbalance might act synergistically to increase mutant frequency. Another interesting result is the production of filaments in the *recA* derivative by ciprofloxacin and trimethoprim treatments. The production of filaments by these antibiotics was believed to be caused by the SOS response, which is mediated by RecA and LexA. This response induces the transcription of the *sulA* (*sfiA*) gene.⁴⁰ SulA interacts reversibly with the protein FtsZ,⁴¹ causing inhibition of cell division and consequent filamentation. *sulA*-independent filamentation is also known in *E. coli*, although this mechanism is also dependent on SOS induction.⁴² Our results suggest that a new SOS-independent mechanism mediates filamentation in the absence of RecA. In fact, we have detected that, at least for ciprofloxacin, filamentation occurs in a *sulA*-deficient background (not shown).

We show here that a number of antibiotics can increase genetic variation by the stimulation of mutagenesis in treated bacteria, suggesting that antibiotic treatments may favour the acquisition and/or evolution of some mechanisms of antibiotic resistance. For instance, some extended-spectrum β -lactamases are the result of combining a reduced number of mutations.⁴³⁻⁴⁶ Thus, sublethal concentrations of mutagenic antimicrobials (not necessarily β -lactams) may accelerate the evolution of new extended-spectrum variants by stimulating the production and accumulation of mutations. Another example is the resistance conferred by increased expression of efflux pumps. It can occur via mutation in different targets, including mutations in the local repressor gene, mutation in a non-related global regulatory gene and changes in the promoter region of the efflux-pump gene (see for instance Piddock⁴⁷).

The stimulatory effect on mutagenesis described here for some of the tested antimicrobials is very low, and may be considered too modest to exert any effect on bacterial evolution. However, it has been stated that modest changes in mutation rate can greatly influence antibiotic resistance development.⁴⁸ As concerns the possibility of finding stimulatory concentrations by a sufficiently dense bacterial population, we have to consider the vast numbers of bacteria challenged by antibiotic treatments. Antibiotics are mainly used to combat pathogens but they also challenge commensals collaterally. While an infection is usually produced by a relatively small number of cells (10^8 - 10^9), $\sim 10^{14}$ prokaryotic cells from hundreds of different species form our commensal flora,⁴⁹ with different intrinsic levels of antibiotic susceptibility. Finally, even resistant microorganisms might be included among the possible targets for the mutagenic effect of antibiotics as high concentrations of antibiotics must be considered sublethal

Figure 3. Effect of antibiotics on cell morphology. Bacterial cultures were treated for 4 h as indicated in the Materials and methods section. (a) Effect on the wild-type strain ME12. (b) Effect on the ME12 *recA* derivative. Bars at the right bottom of each image represent 10 μm . No Ab, no antibiotic; Mito, mitomycin-C; AMP, ampicillin; CAZ, ceftazidime; IPM, imipenem; FOS, fosfomicin; CIP, ciprofloxacin; TMP, trimethoprim; SUL, sulfamethoxazole; SXT, trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole; CST, colistin; TET, tetracycline; GEN, gentamicin; RIF, rifampicin; CHL, chloramphenicol.

for resistant bacteria. Thus, any particular window of sub-MIC mutation-stimulating concentrations of antibiotics should not be difficult to find. The fact that thousands of tons of antibiotics are used every year to treat billions of human and veterinary infections and to promote animal growth increases the probability of finding suitable conditions for the stimulation of mutagenesis.

Studies by Romesberg and coworkers^{8,9} have shown that prevention of SOS activation resulted in a decrease in both survival and mutagenesis in ciprofloxacin-treated cultures, as well as ciprofloxacin or rifampicin-treated infected mice. Consequently, the possibility that components of induced mutation pathways might be inhibited as a novel therapeutic strategy to prevent the development of antibiotic resistance has been proposed.⁵⁰ Efforts have been made to identify small molecules and short peptide inhibitors of RecA activity,^{51–53} although the absence of potential adverse effects on Rad51 (the human RecA homologue) needs to be demonstrated.

Our study aimed to explore the effect of RecA inhibition on induced mutagenesis produced by many antibiotics. Our results with the *recA*-defective strain suggest that most, if not all, mutagenesis induced by sublethal concentrations of antibiotics is dependent, directly or indirectly, on RecA activity, thus supporting the hypothesis that inhibition of RecA is a plausible therapeutic adjuvant in combined therapy to reduce the capacity to generate antibiotic-resistant mutants, with the additional advantages of affecting susceptibility, homologous recombination,²⁰ swarming motility²¹ and biofilms.²²

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Transparency declarations

None to declare.

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